

Mass Spectral Studies of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Magnesium(II)

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Mass spectral studies of the mixed ligand complexes of magnesium(II) of the type MgLL (where HL=salicylaldehyde and HL'=2-hydroxyacetophenone or pentane 2,4 dione) have been carried out and the fragmentation schemes have been suggested.

In an earlier communication the mass spectral studies of several mixed ligand complexes of magnesium(II) with salicylaldehyde, β -diketones and hydroxyaromatic ketones have been reported from these laboratories and the formation of oligometric species has been discussed¹. In the present paper the results of the fragmentation of two such complexes, Mg(sal)(hap) and Mg(sal)(acac) are described.

Experimental

The complexes were synthesised as reported earlier². Mass spectra were recorded on a Kratos MS 25 RF spectrometer (70 eV) at the University of Sheffield, U.K.

Results and Discussion

The mass spectral data are recorded in Table 1. The complex Mg(sal)(hap) showed a less intense molecular ion peak at m/z 280 (3.2%). The fragmentation of the molecule took place through two alternative paths (A and B) as shown in Scheme 1.

Path A: A peak at m/z 238 (10.2%) may be due to the loss of neutral ketene ($\text{CH}_2=\text{C}=\text{O}$) fragment from the molecular ion. Further loss of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$ fragment (93 mass units) from $\text{Mg}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_5\text{O}_2)(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)^+$ species gives a peak at m/z 145 (61.6%) on account of $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$, and this is supported by the appearance of an intense peak at m/z 93 (46.8%) due to the phenoxy fragment. The ion $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ could also be obtained by the direct loss of 2-hydroxyacetophenone moiety from the molecular ion.

Scheme 1. Fragmentation pattern of Mg(sal)(hap)

Path B: A less intense peak at m/z 159 (2.7%) on account of $\text{Mg}(\text{hap})^+$ is observed and this may be due to the loss of $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$ fragment from the molecular ion. This is supported by the appearance of an intense peak at m/z 121 (93%) due to $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$ fragment and another very intense peak at m/z 122 (94%) on account of salicylaldehyde which could have been formed by the abstraction of a proton by the former fragment.

TABLE 1—MASS SPECTRAL DATA AND FRAGMENTATIONS OF Mg(sal)(hap) and Mg(sal)(acac)

Mg(sal)(hap)			Mg(sal)(acac)		
Ion	m/z	Rel. int. %	Ion	m/z	Rel. int. %
M^+	280	3.2	M^+	244	69.4
$(M-42)^+$	238	10.2	$(M-15)^+$	229	53.7
$(M-135)^+$	145	61.6	$(M-42)^+$	202	8.3
$(M-121)^+$	159	2.7	$(M-99)^+$	145	100
	28	100	$(M-28)^+$	216	13
			$(M-121)^+$	123	76.9

Comparison of the intensities of $\text{Mg}(\text{hap})^+$ and $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ ions suggests that $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ is more stable than $\text{Mg}(\text{hap})^+$ which may be due to the more planarity of the chelate ring in $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ ion as compared to $\text{Mg}(\text{hap})^+$ in which the methyl group disturbs the planarity of the chelate ring. Thus the loss of 2-hydroxyacetophenone moiety is more favourable and hence it may be concluded that salicylaldehyde is more strongly bound to the magnesium atom than the 2-hydroxyacetophenone ligand.

In the mass spectrum of the mixed ligand complex $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})(\text{acac})$, a very intense molecular ion peak at m/z 244 (69.4%) is observed. This complex also dissociates through two pathways (A and B) as given in the fragmentation Schemes 2 and 3.

Path A: The loss of odd electron fragment CH_3 from the acetylacetonate moiety of the molecular ion gives rise to an intense peak at m/z 229 (53.7%). Peak at m/z 202 (8.3%) appears due to the loss of neutral ketene fragment ($\text{CH}_2=\text{C}=\text{O}$) from the molecular ion⁹. Loss of acetylacetonate ligand residue (99 mass units) from the mixed ligand complex gives a peak at m/z 145 on account of $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ which is the most abundant species as the peak is of 100% intensity. The ion $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})^+$ appears to be more

Scheme 2 Fragmentation pattern of $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})(\text{acac})$: Path A.

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of $\text{Mg}(\text{sal})(\text{acac})$. Path B

stable due to the presence of the condensed benzene ring in addition to the partially resonance stabilised six-membered chelate ring involving the magnesium atom.

Path B: A peak at m/z 216 (13%) is due to the loss of neutral CO molecule from the salicylaldehyde residue of the molecular ion. Further loss of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$ fragment from $\text{Mg}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{O}_2)(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)^+$ species gives an intense peak at m/z 123 (76.9%) due to the formation of $\text{Mg}(\text{acac})^+$ ion. This is supported by the appearance of a peak at m/z 93 (25%) due to the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}$ fragment. $\text{Mg}(\text{acac})^+$ species could also be obtained by the direct loss of salicylaldehyde residue from the molecular ion. This is supported by the appearance of an intense peak at m/z 121 (71.3%) on account of $\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO}$ fragment and another peak at m/z 122 (78.2%) due to salicylaldehyde which could have been formed by the abstraction of a proton by the former fragment.

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